

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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EVFEMIZMLARNI O`RGATISHDA METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola evfemizmlarning til o`qitishdagi ahamiyati va qo`llanilishida ishlatiladigan metodologik yondashuvlar ta`rifiga qaratilgan bo`lib, unda ushbu iboralar qay tarzda til o`rganuvchilarning nutqini ravon va aniq shakllantirishda yordam berishini o`rganadi. Bilamizki, til o`rganish nafaqat o`sha tilning grammatik tuzilishini, leksikasi, fonetikasini, balki shu tilga bog`liq bo`lgan so`zlashuv madaniyati, iboralarni ham o`rganishni taqozo qiladi. Shu tufayli ham nutqni ravon va mazmunli qilish, noqulay vaziyatlardan erkin chiqib keta olish uchun ham tilga bog`liq bo`lgan evfemizmlarni o`rganish gapirish madaniyatini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Tayanch iboralar: evfemistik iboralar, metod, yondashuv, xushmuomalalik, muloqot madaniyati, evfemistik kategoriya.

KIRISH

Deyarli barcha tillarda evfemistik iboralar mavjud. Evfemizmlar so`zlovchilarga xushmuomalalik bilan gapirishga va qo`pol tilda qiyin xabarlarni ifodalashga imkon beradigan samarali muloqot vositalaridir. Evfemistik iboralar tufayli so`zlovchilar boshqa tinglovchilarning his-tuyg`ularini ranjitishdan saqlaydilar, ularning turli dunyoqarashlariga hurmat ko`rsatadilar, xushmuomala va diplomatik bo`lib qoladilar. Evfemizmlar majoziy tilga tegishli. Ular salbiy ma'noli so'zlarni ijobiy yoki hech bo'lmaganda neytral so'zlar bilan almashtiradilar. Evfemistik tildan foydalanish madaniyatga xos bo`lib, ma'lum bir mamlakatda qabul qilingan me'yorlarni aks ettiradi. Evfemizmlar odatda odamlar suhbatlarida yoki matnlarda uchta asosiy maqsadda qo`llaniladi: ritorika, yumshatish va qochish. Birinchi maqsad orqali ishlatilgan ibora tavsifini o'zgartiramiz, ikkinchisi orqali esa xabarning jiddiyligini kamaytirishga erishamiz. Qochish orqali esa berilgan qo`pol ma'noli so`zni boshqa so`z bilan almashtirishimiz mumkin.

Evfemizmlar tilning asosiy xususiyatlaridan biridir. Ular nafaqat biror tushunchaning haqiqiy ma'nosini yashirish yoki yumshatish uchun xizmat qiladi, balki odamlarning nutqidagi qo`pol, haqoratli g'oyalarni biror yumshatuvchi ibora

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bilan almashtirishda ishlatilishi mumkin. Ochiqroq aytganda, evfemizm - bu juda qo'pol, haqoratli yoki qo'pol ko'rinishi mumkin bo'lgan tilni yashirish, yumshatish yoki boshqa yo'l bilan qo'llash uchun ishlatiladigan muloyim til uslubi hisoblanadi. Xudoyberganova N.R. ning aytishicha, evfemizmlar nafaqat filologiya va tilshunoslikning, balki madaniyatshunoslikning ham o'rganish o'rganish obyekti bo'lishi kerak, chunki bizning davrimizdagi insonlar tobora o'zgarib, qo'pol so'zlardan ko'proq foydalanishyapti. Zero, xushmuomalalik, odob-axloq, xulq-atvor qoidalari, odob-axloq talablarini mensimaydigan odamning kelajagini tasavvur qilish qiyin¹.

Bu borada Rajabkulov O.R. ham o'z fikrini bayon qiladi: "Evfemizmlar tarix davomida qattiq yoki yoqimsiz haqiqatlarni yumshatish va yashirish uchun ishlatilgan. Ushbu lingvistik qurilmalar nozik mavzularni ijtimoiy jihatdan maqbulroq tarzda ifodalash uchun xizmat qiladi²."

Ba'zi holatlarda dars jarayonlarida o'qituvchilar evfemistik iboralardan foydalanishi ta'biy hol. Evfemistik so'zlarni aytganda, o'quvchilarga evfemizmlar qanday yaratilishi va ishlatilishini ham tushuntirish o'qituvchilarning vazifasi hisoblanadi. Ushbu jarayon o'qituvchilarga evfemizmga yo'naltirilgan vaziyatni tashkil qilish va ulardan sinfda ko'proq foydalanish o'quvchilarning muomala madaniyatini shakllantirishda ko'maklashadi. Ushbu masalada Anna Bloch o'z fikrini qo'shib qoyadi: "O'qituvchi va o'quvchining ijobiy o'zaro munosabati, albatta, ta'lim maqsadlariga erishishning zaruriy tarkibiy qismidir. Bu o'qituvchi va uning talabalari o'rtasida o'zaro tushunish va hurmatga asoslangan mazmunli muloqotni ta'minlaydi. Shuningdek, u o'quvchilarning sinf faoliyatida ishtirok etishini nazarda tutadi³."

Ko'pgina tadqiqotchilarning fikricha, evfemizmlarning katta qismi semantik jihatdan noaniqdir. Ya'ni ularning matndan tashqarida ma'nosini anglab olishda o'quvchilarda muammolar yuzaga kelishi mumkin. O'quvchilar uchun esa evfemizmlar tilning asosan o'qitilmagan qismini ifodalaydi. Biznes vakillari, ommaviy axborot vositalari vakillari ma'lumotni haqiqiylikini tekshirish uchun har qanday ma'lumotlarni dekodlash ya'ni ma'nosini ochishga harakat qilishdai.

¹ Khudaybergenova, Nodira Rustamovna. "The theory of English euphemisms and their peculiar features in language teaching methodology." *Проблемы педагогики* 9 (2017): 96-98.

² Radjabkulov O. R. "Euphemisms and their role in communication." International scientific online conference(2023), Vol.4, №9.

³ Bloch-Rozmej, Anna. "Euphemisms and teacher-student interactions." *Linguistics Beyond and Within (LingBaW)* 9 (2023): 6-22.

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Bunday toifa vakillariga har qanday bo`rttirish, qochirmalardan yiroq ma`lumot zarurdir.

Chamizo Dominguez va Sánchez Benedito evfemizmlarning beshta asosiy funksiyasini aniqlaydi⁴. Evfemistik iboralardan foydalangan holda, ma'ruzachilar assotsiativ yoki kontseptual muhandislik jarayonini amalga oshiradilar, bu orqali ular ijobiy yoki neytral tomonlarini ochib berish orqali xabarning qo`pol ma`nolarini yashiradilar. Mualliflar ijobiy ijtimoiy munosabatlarni mustahkamlash maqsadida ham evfemizmlardan foydalanishadi.

Muomala madaniyatida odatda qo`pol va vahimali bo'lgan tushunchalar (masalan, urush, kasallik, o'lim) haqida gapirish uchun maxsus evfemistik iboralardan foydalanadilar. Xuddi shunday, o`qituvchilar ham sinfda ishlatiladigan qo`pol so`zlar o`rniga evfemizmlar foydalanishi mumkin. Evfemizmlarning o`z vaziyatiga qarab qo`llanilishi bu o`qituvchining sinfdagi maqomini ko`taradi va o`quvchilarga o`rnak qilib ko`rsatadi.

ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Evfemizmlarning qo`llanilishi va o`rgatilishi bo`yicha tadqiqot olib borgan bir nechta manbaalar topildi. Shulardan Kabilova S. A.⁵ evfemizmlarning lingvistik tasnifi bo`yicha, Kamalova F.O.⁶ evfemizmlarning muloqotdagi ahamiyati haqida, Zokirov M. va Isomiddinov F.⁷ esa evfemizmlar borasida turli yondashuvlarni tahlil qilib chiqishgan. Bundan tashqari Djalilova Z.B.⁸ evfemizmlarning muomaladagi o`rnini alohida o`rganib chiqqan. Rahimov F. R.⁹ esa evfemizmlarning o`zbek tili doirasida qo`llanilishiga alohida e`tibor qaratgan. Rahmonova G. X.¹⁰ ingliz tilida qo`llaniladigan evfemizmlarning pragmatik xususiyatlari bo`yicha tadqiqot olib borgan.

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⁴ Chamizo Domínguez, P. J., and F. Sánchez Benedito. 2005. *Conceptual Networks of English Bawdy Euphemisms and Dysphemisms*. Unpublished manuscript.

⁵ Abduraimovna, Sayyora Kabilova. "Evfemizmlarning asosiy lingvistik tasniflari." *Conferencea* (2023): 12-15.

⁶ Omiljonovna, Kamalova Feruza. "Evfemizmlarning muloqot va badiiy nutqdagi ahamiyati." *Innovation in the modern education system* 3.27 (2023): 261-263.

⁷ Zokirov, M., and F. Isomiddinov. "Evfemizmlar borasidagi turli yondashuvlar xususida." *Редакционная коллегия* (2021).

⁸ Djalilova, Zarnigor. "Gender xushmuomalalikka asoslangan iboralarning shakllanishi." *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика* 1.28 (2022): 303-308.

⁹ Rahimov, Fayziddin Rustamovich. "O`zbek tilida evfemizmlar va ularning qo`llanish doirasi." *International Conferences*. Vol. 1. No. 6. 2022.

¹⁰ Rahmonova, Gulhayo Xalilovna. "Ingliz tilidagi evfemizmlarning pragmatik xususiyatlari." *Innovative Development in Educational Activities* 2.24 (2023): 79-82.

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Tadqiqotni amalga oshirish maqsadida ushbu evfemizlar metodologiyasiga oid bir qancha metodlar va mashqlar topildi. Har bir topshiriq evfemizlarning o'rganilish darajasi, tartibi, usuliga qarab ta'riflab chiqildi. Albatta har qanday yondashuv va metod ham o'quvchilarning bilim darajasi, o'zlashtirish qobiliyatiga qarab o'zgartiriladi va moslashtiriladi.

Rahimova F. aytadiki: "Har bir xalq nutqi madaniyatining bir bo'lagi sifatida shakllanadi. Bu o'sha xalqning so'zlashuv madaniyatida yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi¹¹". Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, nutq madaniyatini evfemizmlar orqali shakllantirish so'zlashuv vaziyatini ancha yumshatadi.

Evfemizmlarni o'rgatishga qaratilgan darsni barcha tillar mavjud bo'lgani kabi o'qitilayotgan tilda ham qiyin bo'lgan mavzular borligini tushuntirish bilan boshlash kerak. Ushbu mavzular uchun biz asl so'zlarga qaraganda "yumshoq" so'zlar bo'lgan evfemizmlar deb ataladigan so'zlardan foydalanish kerakligi darsning boshida tushuntiriladi.

O'qituvchi darsni boshlaganidan doskaga salbiy ma'noli bildiruvchi so'zlarni yozib, avvalo bunday so'zlar o'rnida qo'llaniluvchi qanday yumshatuvchi so'zlar borligi haqida so'rab "brainstorming" qilish mumkin. Masalan, "kambag'al" so'zining atrofiga unga mos keluvchi evfemizmlarni yozib chiqib tushuncha hosil qilish mumkin. Bundan tashqari salbiy ma'noli "semiz", "qari", "xunuk" so'zlarini evfemizatsiya qilishni vazifa sifati berish mumkin. Ingliz tilida "poor" so'zining o'rniga "low-income", "old" so'zining o'rniga esa "senior, mature" kabi so'zlarni qo'llash mumkinligini aytish mumkin. Bundan tashqari "fat" so'zining o'rniga "overweight", "portly" yoki "husky" kabi so'zlarning qo'llanilishi ancha maqsadga muvofiq bo'lishini tushuntirish kerak.

Evfemizmlarni faqat lingvistik atamalar orqali tushunish qiyin. Bunday so'zlarni chuqurroq ma'nosini ochib berish uchun ular qatnashgan gaplarni doskaga yozib, talabalardan alohida belgilangan jumlar qaysi so'zning o'rnida qo'llanganligini so'rashi mumkin:

- His grandfather *passed away*-Uning bobosi *vafot etgan*.
- My father is *between jobs* but has two interviews today-Otam hozircha *ishsiz*, ammo bugun u ikki joyga suhbatga borishi kerak.

¹¹ Rahimov, Fayziddin Rustomovich. "O'zbek tilida evfemizmlar va ularning qo'llanish doirasi." *International Conferences*. Vol. 1. No. 6. 2022.

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- The peace officer apprehended the *sanitation man* for speeding- Tinchlik nazorati xizmati xodimi *tozalik nazoratchisini* tezlikni oshirgani uchun ushladi.
- Our son is *a special child*- Bizning farzandimiz *o`zgacha bola*.
- Dan's supervisor laid him off because he was *unmotivated*- Danning rahbari uni *ishtiyoqsizligi* uchun ishdan bo'shatdi.
- The correctional facility has 220 *inmates*, five of whom are facing *capital punishment*- Axloq tuzatish muassasasida 220 nafar *mahbus* bor, ulardan besh nafari *o'lim jazosiga hukm qilingan*.

Evfemizlar haqida yanada chuqurroq tushunchaga ega bo`lish uchun o`quvchilarga “Ma`nolarni moslashtirish” kabi mashqni bajartirish ham qo`l keladi. Masalan, qo`pol so`zlar bir jadval qilinadi va yon tomonida ularga mos evfemizistik so`zlar beriladi. O`quvchilarning fikrlashini kengaytirish uchun bu birikmalar aralashtirib tashlanishi kerak:

So`zlar	Evfemizlar
O`lmoq	Ayollar(erkaklar xonasi)
Hojatxona	Tejamkor
Kambag`al	Vafot etmoq
Xunuk	O`zgacha ko`rinishga ega
Baxil	Moddiy kam ta`minlangan
Yig`lamoq	Ko`zi qizarmoq

Shunga o`xshash mashqlarni o`quvchilar butun guruh bo`lib ham bajarishlari mumkin. Bunda o`quvchilarning har biriga so`zlar va evfemizmlar bo`lib beriladi va o`z sheriklarini topish maqsadida ular izlanishadi.

Bingo. Evfemizmlar yozilgan bingo kartalarini taxlab, o'quvchilarga ularning ma`nosini tushuntirishi kerakligi tushuntiriladi. Har bir to`g`ri topilgan javibga “bingo” so`zi aytiladi.

Xotira mashqi. Ushbu topshiriqni amalga oshirish uchun o`quvchilarga evfemizmlar qo`llanilgan matnlar beriladi va mustaqil topshiriq sifatida nechta evfemizmlar qo`llanilganligi haqida so`raladi. O`quvchilar o`zlari topib, belgilab ma`nosini anglashga harakat qilishadi. Mashqning oxirida esa kim qanday evfemizmlar topganligi va nechtasini eslab qolganligi haqida so`raladi.

Hikoya yozish mashqi. Ushbu topshiriqdan o`quvchilarning ijodkorlik qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish maqsadida qo`llaniladi. O`qituvchi 5-6 ta

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evfemizmlarni doskaga yozib, uyda ushbu soʻzlar yordamida hikoya yozib kelish topshirigʻini beradi. Oʻquvchilar soʻzlarni mazmunan bir-biri bilan bogʻlab, qiziqarli hikoya tuzib kelishga harakat qilishadi. Doskaga yozilgan soʻzlardan tashqari qoʻshimcha evfemizmlardan ham foydalanish mumkin.

Hikoyani tinglash. Ushbu topshiriq orqali oʻqituvchi bir necha darsning maqsadlarini amalga oshirishi mumkin. Evfemistik iboralardan tashkil topgan hikoyani oʻqis davomida oʻquvchilar uni tinglashadi va oʻz-oʻzini baholash strategiyasini amalga oshirishlari mumkin. Tinglash davomida qaysi soʻzning oʻrniga qanday evfemizmlar qoʻllanilganini aytib, bir-birini baholashadi.

Darsni mustahkamlash maqsadida oʻquvchilardan mustahkamlovchi savollarni soʻrash darsning asl maqsadga erishishga xizmat qiladi:

-Evfemizmlarni qanday hollarda qoʻllash maʼqul yoki maʼqul emas?

-Yangiliklar haqida xabar berilganda jurnalistlar evfemizmlardan foydalanishi qanchalik toʻgʻri?

-Muomala madaniyatining shakllanishida evfemizmlar qanday rol oʻynaydi?

XULOSA

Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi oʻqituvchilarning evfemizm fenomeniga munosabatini va uning oʻqituvchi va oʻquvchining oʻzaro munosabatlaridagi rolini aniqlash, oʻquvchilarga ushbu iboralarni yetkazishga qaratilgan edi. Biz oʻqituvchilar evfemizm va ijodkorlik oʻrtasidagi bogʻliqlik turli xil topshiriqlar orqali oʻquvchilarga yetkazib bera olishiga guvoh boʻldik. Ijtimoiy hayotda evfemizmlardan foydalanish munosabat sifati va samaradorligiga ijobiy taʼsir qilishi mumkinligiga amin boʻldik. Tadqiqotchilarning fikricha, oʻqituvchi va oʻquvchining ogʻzaki almashinuviga evfemistik iboralarni kiritishdan maqsad bir-birining dunyoqarashi va qadriyatlariga hurmat koʻrsatishdir. Ushbu tadqiqotda keltirilgan xulosalarga asoslanib, evfemizmlar oʻqituvchi va talaba munosabatlariga ijobiy taʼsir koʻrsatishning katta salohiyatiga ega ekanligini taʼkidlash mumkin.

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